

A NEW CHARACTERIZATION TEST FOR COMPOSITE RINGS IN TENSION AND COMPRESSION

O..KADOUCH, Th. MASSARD, JP. ANSART
COMISSARIAT A L'ENERGIE ATOMIQUE
BP N° 12 - 91680 Bruyères -le-Châtel - Paris - France

ABSTRACT

The mechanical characterization of unidirectional composite materials is complex because of their strong anisotropy. The loading conditions have to be closely examined. Tension and compression tests on rings are interesting since they don't require mechanical bonds and because it's a direct way to test filament wound materials. A specific device has been designed for tension test (internal pressure) and for compression test (external pressure). This test is not only very simple (one can be performed on most tensile machines) but it can also be used to characterize some composite materials in temperature using different pressure transmitters.

1. INTRODUCTION

During usual tensile or compressive test [1], uniform stress is generated in rings using a liner pressurized with a fluid (silicon oil). To simplify the process we have developed a test using an elastomer as pressure transmitter. These two tests have been performed on a graphite/epoxy composite.

2. EXPERIMENTS

2-1. SAMPLES CHARACTERISTICS

The composite we have characterized is made from the preimpregnated T300/M10

MATRIX

Composite's matrix is an epoxy resin M10 which properties are following :

Density (g/cm ³)	1,2
Young's Modulus (GPa)	3,15
Poisson's ratio	0,3
Glass transition temperature (°C)	110-140

FIBERS

The carbon fibers are Torray fibers T300-3000 which properties are following :

Physical properties

density (g/cm ³)	1,75
filament count	3000
mass per unit length (g/1000m)	198

Mechanical properties

Young's Modulus (GPa)	230
Tensile strength (GPa)	3,528
Elongation at fracture (%)	1,5

RINGS GEOMETRY

The rings are made using the filament winding technics. The fibers orientation is thus circumferential.

Rings dimensions:	height (mm)	21
	internal diameter (mm)	130
	thickness (mm)	1,1

2-2 RINGS 'EXPANSION TEST' : EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDUREPRESSURE TRANSMITTER : LINER

We have carried out an expansion test (internal pressure) to characterize longitudinal Young's Modulus E_x , tensile strength, Poisson's ratio and elongation at fracture. This test [1] consists in subjecting the ring to a uniform and uniaxial internal pressure with a liner pressurized with silicon oil. The ring is introduced between two shields : their spacing is adjusted to be equal to the ring length.

Figure 1 :Rings ' expansion test' (internal liner)

Figure 2 :Top view

SILASTENE PRESSURE TRANSMITTER TYPE

To simplify the process we have substituted the liner by a silastene joint (RTV 860 rhodorsil) which is directly injected in the device. This one is then inserted in a ZWICK 1687 tensile machine to generate the required pressure.

Figure 3 :Silastene pressure transmitter type

3 RESULTS

3-1 MECHANICAL CHARACTERISTICS

The ring ratio of thickness to diameter is small enough to approximate the tensile stress σ_r by the following expression(2):

$$\sigma_r = (P \cdot R / e)$$

with , R the average ring radius, e the thickness of the ring and P the pressure induced to the internal surface of the ring.

- For the silastene pressure transmitter type :

$$P = F / S$$

with , F the strength applied by the machine and S the surface in contact between the brass ring and the silastene.

- For the liner pressure transmitter type P is the oil pressure.

We find :

$$\sigma_r = 1558 \text{MPa} , A_r = 1,06\% , \nu = 0,2 \text{ and } E_x = 144 \text{GPa}$$

The mechanical performances of the rings seem higher with the elastomer

$$\sigma_r = 1951 \text{MPa} , A_r = 1,2\% , \nu = 0,3 \text{ and } E_x = 149 \text{GPa}$$

3-2 COMPARISON OF THE TWO TYPES OF TESTS

The Young's modulus found with the new test are closed to the theoretical ones we have determined from the mixing law (E_m matrix's modulus, E_f fibers' modulus, v_f fibers' ratio):

$$E = v_f * E_f + (1 - v_f) E_m$$

With $E_f = 230 \text{ GPa}$, $v_f = 0,65$ and $E_m = 31 \text{ GPa}$
it comes $E = 160 \text{ GPa}$.

The expansion test has to be exclusively uniaxial because of the strong material anisotropy. Figure 4 shows the quadratic failure criterion in the strain space.

Figure 4 : Quadratic failure criterion in the strain space

It shows a small shear and a low transverse tension.

The fact that the transverse traction is higher in the liner device (coefficient of the Poisson's ratio below the theoretical value) can easily be explained : when the liner is under pressure ,its volume increases whereas the ring height decreases. When the adherence is high enough the ring is subjected to a small transverse traction and its shrinkage is disturbed. Shear is due to the peculiar conditions of the test. The pressurized liner fills the gap between the ring and the shields, and expands above the ring. It creates a shear stress as shown in figure 5.

Figure 5 :Oil injection in the liner

5-CONCLUSIONS

We have presented a new method for mechanical characterization of composite rings. The use of an elastomeric pressure transmitter instead of the usual liner seems advantageous. This test is not only easy to perform but it's closer to an uniaxial test (which is not always the case with a liner pressure transmitter type).

Besides, measurements in high temperature can be made. We are now characterizing composite rings with metallic matrix (Aluminium /SiC composites) at 340°C. The viscosity of the new pressure transmitter at 340°C must be equal to the silastene viscosity at room temperature. The PEEK (polyethersulfone) seems to be attractive. Its glass transition temperature (334°C) enables us to characterize the ring mechanical performance between 340°C and 350°C.

Finally with specific measurement devices (strain gages ,acoustic emission sensors) this type of apparatus could provide a whole characterization of a wound material and this for low cost

REFERENCES

- [1] "Composite Design " 4Th ed S.W. Tsai Think composite ed
- [2] "Resistance des matériaux " Timoshenko Librairie polytechnique